

Enhancing affective and continuance commitment to the organization through affective and cognitive attitude toward work

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to examine the influence of attitude toward work on the organizational commitment of employees. To deepen the concept of the study, literatures were reviewed. The study applied descriptive assessment and correlational research design. The population was all employees of the institution. Questionnaires were used to gather the data and inferential statistics were used to analyze the data. The study found that the attitudes of employees toward their work and organizational commitment were high. The analysis of variance suggests that overall, there is a significant correlation between attitude and organizational commitment. However, taking it singly, there is no correlation between attitude and normative organizational commitment. Thus, the study suggests that management needs to enhance employees' organizational commitment through improving affective and cognitive attitudes toward work...

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Introduction

Achieving organizational success requires not only careful planning and financial support but also attention to the psychological dimension of human resources. Effective management of human resources involves focusing not only on employees' knowledge and skills but also on their attitudes toward the organization, their work, and their colleagues. Positive attitudes in these areas significantly enhance employee performance and organizational

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citizenship behavior (Allameh et al., 2012). Neglecting the attitudinal aspects of employees can lead to performance deficiencies, decreased commitment, and reduced organizational citizenship behavior, ultimately impacting organizational success (Tian, 2022).

Recognizing its crucial role in organizational performance, researchers have extensively studied human attitudes toward various objects. Thurstone (1928) conceptualized attitude as a multifaceted construct, arguing that it represents an individual's evaluation of a given object. This idea was expanded by later researchers, including Katz and Stotland (1959), Rosenberg and Hovland (1960), and Zanna and Rempel (1988), who developed the tripartite theory of attitude encompassing affective, cognitive, and behavioral dimensions. This theory is supported by Breckler (1984), Kothandapani (1971), and Ostrom (1969), who classified evaluative judgments into these three response categories. According to Ajzen (1993) and Maio and Haddock (2010), cognitive and affective judgments influence behavior, meaning that a person's latent attitude toward an object should be reflected in their manifest behavior (Kaiser & Wilson, 2019).

Numerous studies have explored the impact of attitudes on behavior, including Ajzen and Fishbein (1970, 1977, 1980, 2000), Ajzen and Driver (1992), Ajzen and Sexton (1999), and Ajzen and Fishbein (2005). These studies confirm that attitude is a strong predictor of behavior. Brugger and Hochli (2019) found that strong attitudes lead to spillover behavior, where initial behavior increases the likelihood of engaging in additional behavior that supports the same goal. This study argued that repeated behaviors reflect the strength of an attitude. Building on this concept, the current study examines the effect of attitudes on organizational commitment. To date, no studies have investigated the impact of cognitive and affective attitudes toward work on affective, continuance, and normative organizational commitment.

In the context of private education, a significant challenge is faculty turnover, often with teachers moving from private to public schools. While the assumption is that such moves are motivated by the prospect of better opportunities, they may also result from attitudes toward teaching or their work. This study aims to explore employees' attitudes toward their work and how these attitudes affect their affective, continuance, and normative organizational commitment.

The study is structured into five parts: the introduction, which outlines the study's background; the literature review, covering theories of attitude and organizational commitment; the research methodology, detailing the research design, population, locale, data collection procedures, research instruments, ethical considerations, and statistical analysis; the data presentation and analysis, which includes tabular data and subsequent analysis; and the results and discussion, which interpret the study's findings and their implications, followed by a conclusion.

Literature Review

A literature review enables the researcher to grasp the concept of the study and identify the specific problems to be investigated. It includes only literature directly relevant to the current topic.

Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

Attitude and Behavior

Many researchers have studied attitude; however, as Chaiklin (2011) admitted, there is no universally accepted definition or measurement agreed upon by all scholars. This confusion can lead to various approaches to studying attitude, resulting in reduced explanatory power in several studies, as Myers (1977) noted. To study and measure the concept accurately, a more precise definition of attitude should be formulated (Altman, 2008). To this end, one must consult dictionaries that define the term attitude and examine scholarly definitions. The Cambridge Dictionary (n.d.) defines attitude as “a feeling or opinion about something or someone, or a way of behaving that is caused by this.”

This definition identifies three characteristics of attitude: feeling (affective), opinion (cognitive), and behavior (conative). The Merriam-Webster Dictionary defines it as “a mental position concerning a fact or state” or “a feeling or emotion toward a fact or state,” emphasizing the cognitive and affective dimensions of attitude. Collins Dictionary defines it as “a way how one thinks and feels about something, especially when this shows in the way one behaves,” describing attitudes as ideas, feelings, and behavior. Thus, idea, feeling, and behavior are inseparable components of attitude, representing automatic reactions or responses when facing certain objects or people.

Since attitude is a psychological concept, it is helpful to consider how psychology defines it. In psychology, an attitude refers to a “set of emotions, beliefs, and behavior toward a certain object, person, or event” (Cherry, 2022). This definition still identifies three dimensions of attitudes as indicated by the dictionaries. The APA Dictionary of Psychology (2023) defines it as “a relatively enduring and general evaluation of an object, person, group, issue, or concept on a dimension ranging from negative to positive.” In other words, it is an evaluative judgment of an external stimulus such as persons, objects, or events, resulting in positive and negative reactions/evaluations (Seel, 2012). Such evaluative judgment is derived from specific beliefs, emotions, and past behaviors associated with those objects, persons, or events. Psychologists commonly define attitude as a learned tendency to evaluate or respond to things in a certain way (Chaiklin, 2011). This is similar to the definition given by Hogg and Vaughan (2005, p. 150), who defined it as “a relatively enduring organization of beliefs, feelings, and behavioral tendencies towards socially significant objects, groups, events, or symbols.” Eagly and Chaiken (1993, 2005) further defined it as “a psychological tendency that is expressed by evaluating a particular entity with some degree of favor or disfavor.” Attitude as an evaluative judgment results from upbringing or experience with certain objects, persons, or events, and therefore, it can be changed. The debate continues on whether behavior should change first before attitude or vice versa (Dollard, 1949; Krech & Crutchfield, 1948; Kutner, Wilkins, & Yarrow, 1970; Lewin, 1999), but consensus suggests that changing attitude must come first. The study by Unal and Sari (2012) recommended that improving learners' interest in a subject can be achieved by teaching positive values related to the subject to change or reverse their negative attitude toward it.

The impact of attitude on behavior has been studied extensively, but findings do not always align, suggesting that attitude and actual behavior are not always perfectly correlated (Chaiklin, 2011). This is supported by evidence from studies measuring the correlation between attitude and behavior, which have yielded mixed results. Some studies have found a positive correlation between attitude and behavior, while others have shown a negative correlation (Wicker, 1969). LaPiere (1934) found no correlation between attitude and behavior in his study. Wicker (1969) reviewed approximately 49 studies, which resulted in conflicting findings. Schuman and Johnson (1976) also reviewed literature on the relationship between attitude and behavior and found that the correlation ranged from small to moderate. The works of Wicker (1969) and Schuman and Johnson (1976) renewed scholarly interest in the effects of attitude on behavior and challenged Wicker's conclusions. Schuman and Johnson (1976) suggested improving attitudinal measures, developing multiple indicators of behavior, investigating nonattitudinal forces influencing behavior, and identifying behaviors that cannot be predicted from attitudinal responses. Their findings align with earlier research by Campbell, Converse, Miller, and Stokes (1960), which found a strong correlation between attitude toward a political leader and voting behavior. This result encouraged further research into the attitude-behavior relationship, incorporating Schuman and Johnson's (1976) recommendations. Heberlein and Black (1976), and Ajzen (1991) also contributed to resolving these conflicting findings, suggesting a strong correlation between attitude and behavior. Ajzen and Fishbein (2005) argued in the Theory of Reasoned Action that people's behavior originates from their beliefs, attitudes, and intentions. This argument is consistent with Cognitive Consistency Theory, which suggests that people seek consistency among their attitudes and align their behavior to appear rational and consistent (Sinha, 2022). The theory supports the notion that attitudes lead to behavior (Ajzen & Fishbein, 2005). Kraus (2016) conducted a study on attitudes predicting behavior and confirmed a significant correlation between attitude and behavior. However, conflicting findings can be explained by confusion between general attitudes toward physical objects or groups and specific attitudes toward performing behaviors (Ajzen & Fishbein, 2005). Additionally, mixed results may arise from other social factors. Attitude is not the sole predictor of

behavior; multiple factors must be considered (Frymier & Nadler, 2017), as recommended by Schuman and Johnson (1976). Fishbein and Ajzen (1975) and Ajzen (1991) noted that attitude is not the only factor influencing behavior. They identified three elements necessary for attitude to produce behavior: attitude toward the behavior (the stronger the attitude, the better), subjective norms (support from influential persons), and perceived behavioral control (self-efficacy). LaPiere (1936) argued that an attitude will likely manifest in behavior if the social situation allows it.

Given these controversies, researchers continue to study the correlation between attitude and behavior, believing that attitude is a predictor of human behavior. Studies on this correlation commonly focus on several elements, namely affective, cognitive, and behavioral dimensions. The tripartite model proposed by Rosenberg and Hovland (1960) was used to study human attitude and behavior, based on the belief that latent variables such as affective and cognitive elements of attitude are displayed through manifest behavior (verbal and nonverbal reactions). Glasman and Albarracín (2006) conducted a meta-analysis and found a significant correlation between attitude and behavior, arguing that affective and cognitive attitudes affect behavior. Based on this study, current researchers maintain that attitudes affect behavior. In the present study, two dimensions of the tripartite attitude model— affective and cognitive aspects, the latent elements of attitude—will be measured, with behavior assessed through employees' verbal reactions related to their organizational commitment. The goal is to determine if latent attitudes of affection and cognition manifest through employees' commitment to the organization.

Tripartite Model of Attitude: Affective, Cognitive and Behavioral Model.

Affective Attitude: one's emotion toward something

Affective attitude has been discussed within the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) and the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB). TRA posits that behavior is solely influenced by the intention to perform a behavior, which is determined by the attitude toward the behavior and subjective norms (Ajzen & Fishbein, 1975; Fishbein & Ajzen, 1980). In contrast, TPB extends this by including perceived behavioral control, suggesting that individuals act rationally according to their attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived control over the behavior. While TRA emphasizes that behavior is driven by intention, TPB argues that perceived behavioral control—comprising self-efficacy (one's belief in their own abilities) (Bandura, 1991) and perceived controllability (the belief that one's behavior is under volitional control) (Ajzen, 2002)—also predicts intention and behavior (Ajzen, 1988, 1991; Kan & Fabrigar, 2017). According to TRA and TPB, salient behavioral beliefs and outcome evaluations predict attitudes, which in turn predict intentions and actual behavior (French et al., 2005). Within these theories, affective attitude is defined as “emotions and drives engendered by the prospect of performing a behavior” (French et al., 2005). The affective component of an attitude involves a person's feelings or emotions toward the attitude object. When encountering another person, act, or object, an individual has an emotional reaction—either positive or negative—that influences their attitude and behavior, leading to a welcoming or avoiding response (McLeod, 2018). This assumption posits that a person's behavior is consistent with their attitude. Research has demonstrated a significant correlation between affective attitude and behavioral intention (Godin, 1987; Lowe, Eves, & Carroll, 2002; Valois, Desharnais, & Godin, 1988; Ajzen & Driver, 1992; Trafimow et al., 2004).

In the context of the current investigation, an affective attitude toward work refers to one's feelings or emotions about their work. Positive or negative feelings toward work can influence an individual's behavior regarding their job (Abun et al., 2021). Therefore, fostering positive feelings about work can enhance work performance and commitment (Shripria et al., 2021).

Cognitive Attitude

Social psychologists contend that cognition involves the mental activity of processing information from external stimuli and using that information to make evaluations and judgments, which help in understanding and predicting our own and others' behavior (Festinger, 1957). Cognitive attitude is part of the tripartite model of attitude proposed

by Katz and Stotland (1959), Rosenberg and Hovland (1960), and Zanna and Rempel (1988). This model includes affective, cognitive, and behavioral components. Cognitive attitude refers to a person's thoughts, mental perceptions, or ideas about a particular person, object, event, or action (Abun et al., 2019). It also encompasses a person's beliefs or knowledge about an attitude object (McLeod, 2018). Malhotra (2005) argued that it is a summary evaluation of an attitude object, resulting in either a like or dislike attitude (Thurstone, 1931). This evaluation occurs after a person encounters an object or person, gathers information about it, processes, and stores it (Greenwald et al., 1966), leading to cognitive and affective attitudes, or it can stem from education, upbringing, observation, and media influence (Olufemi, 2012). The processed information is stored in memory and may originate from empirical data, observation, experimentation, and interpretation (Luthans, 2008).

The more frequently a person hears or is exposed to an attitude, the more likely they are to adopt it (Olufemi, 2012). The strength of cognitive attitude is theorized to depend on the value importance and perceived instrumentality of the attitude object (Rosenberg, 1956), suggesting that people develop more knowledge or thoughts about an object that holds significant value or usefulness for them (McLeod, 2018). Some cognitive attitudes are stronger toward certain objects because individuals find them important for guiding their behavior (Ferguson, Bargh, & Nayak, 2005).

The effect of attitude on behavior can vary. Millar and Tesser (1990) found that behavior can be driven by either affective or cognitive attitudes. Their research suggested that behavior performed for its own sake is likely driven by affective attitude, while behavior aimed at achieving a predetermined objective is driven by cognitive attitude. Albarracín and Wyer (2000) argued that past behavior influences the decision to repeat or not repeat a behavior, partly through cognitive activity that informs the actor of specific behavioral consequences. Later research by Ajzen and Fishbein (2005) confirmed that attitude and behavior are significantly correlated. This conclusion aligns with Allport's (1935) earlier argument that attitude influences individual responses to objects, people, or situations, a view still supported by Ajzen and Fishbein (1970, 1975). However, Zhou et al. (2013) cautioned that the relationship between attitude and behavior is not straightforward, as cognitive and affective consistency play a moderating role.

Cognitive attitude toward work refers to one's ideas or mental perceptions about their work (Abun et al., 2021). It reflects what one believes about the work. Individuals may have either negative or positive perceptions of the same work, and these cognitive attitudes can affect their behavior (Susanty & Miradipta, 2013). Thus, fostering a positive cognitive attitude toward one's work can improve work performance (Abun et al., 2021).

The philosophy of work

Affective and cognitive attitudes toward work do not arise automatically; they result from individuals' understanding and experience of their work. Consequently, not all employees will share the same attitude toward their work. This variation is not limited to ordinary people but also applies to scholars. The diversity in attitudes is not only due to differing experiences or upbringing but also because the term "work" can refer to many different things. For example, one might hear the advice to "work it out" when trying to lose weight, resolve a broken relationship, or regain hope. This ambiguity is why some philosophers argue that "work" resists a clear definition (Muirhead, 2007; Svendsen, 2015) or is considered a loose concept (Pence, 2001). Despite the challenge of defining work, it is essential to understand it meaningfully.

To guide our discussion, we need a conceptual map to better understand work. We will start by examining dictionary definitions of work and then explore various expert perspectives. Oxford Languages (n.d.) defines work as "activity involving mental or physical effort done to achieve a purpose or result" or "a task or tasks to be undertaken." Merriam-Webster (n.d.) defines it as "to perform work or fulfill duties regularly for wages or salary" or "to exert oneself physically or mentally, especially in sustained effort for a purpose or under compulsion or necessity" or "to produce a desired effect or result." These definitions suggest that work is not necessarily synonymous with

employment, as not all work involves formal employment (Cholbi, 2022). Therefore, work can be summarized as a physical and mental activity performed to achieve a desired end or objective.

Richard (1998) defines work as "an activity that involves a significant effort to achieve a goal beyond enjoyment," indicating that work serves the dual purposes of achieving goals and providing enjoyment. According to Appiah (2021), the purpose of work may include producing goods and services necessary for sustaining life, for which workers receive wages. However, Appiah also raises an ethical question: how can work contribute to a good life? This expands Richard's (1998) definition to include not just survival and financial gain but also enjoyment and self-expression. Work enables self-realization through goal attainment and allows workers to express themselves. For work to be a form of self-expression, workers must have freedom or autonomy in performing their tasks (Richard, 1998). As self-expression, work reflects self-identity and shapes one's sense of self (Smith, 2016; Pence, 2016). Smith (2016) suggests that the workplace should provide conditions for meaningful and rewarding work, contributing to a good life. This concept introduces the notion of work as a calling (Pence, 2016). Work as a calling implies that individuals derive intrinsic pleasure from their work and identify with it, finding a higher purpose beyond mere financial gain, such as serving the community or a religious calling (Cholbi, 2022).

These concepts reveal that work is not just labor or workmanship but also has moral and religious dimensions (Pence, 2016). Pence (2016) distinguishes between labor, workmanship, and calling: labor involves repetitive tasks that are not intrinsically satisfying and offer little choice, while workmanship requires higher human faculties, provides intrinsic satisfaction, and allows for some degree of choice and pride. The moral concept of work involves developing and exercising unique personal qualities, finding intrinsic satisfaction in the activity, and having personal choice in accepting the job (Pence, 2016). Whether work is categorized as labor, workmanship, or a calling depends on the worker's perception and experience. For example, even if one works as an accountant, if the work is repetitive and lacks personal choice, it is considered labor. Conversely, if the work is a personal choice and provides intrinsic satisfaction, it could be classified as workmanship or a calling if it also serves the community (Pence, 2016).

The concept of organizational commitment: a multidimensional dimensional perspective

Organizational commitment is grounded in social exchange theory and reciprocity norms (Gouldner, 1960). The theory posits that individuals are likely to help those who have helped them. This concept is particularly relevant in the organizational context, where the employer-employee relationship benefits both parties (Khan & Iqbal, 2020a). Given its importance in managing a successful organization, scholars have extensively investigated the significance of organizational commitment. It is a complex and multidimensional construct, and while scholars have identified various dimensions of organizational commitment, there is not universal agreement on which dimensions are most pertinent.

For example, Meyer and Allen (1997) identified three dimensions of organizational commitment: affective, continuance, and normative commitment. In contrast, O'Reilly and Chatman (1986) classified organizational commitment into compliance, identification, and internalization. The debate continued when Wechsler (1996) proposed another set of dimensions: identification, affiliation, and exchange. However, upon evaluation, the content of the dimensions presented by O'Reilly and Chatman (1986) and Wechsler (1996) is largely captured by Meyer and Allen's (1997) dimensions. Therefore, this paper adopts Meyer and Allen's (1997) framework, which includes affective, continuance, and normative commitment, as the basis for investigating organizational commitment.

Scholars also distinguish between two conceptualizations of commitment: attitudinal and behavioral. Affective commitment pertains to an employee's psychological attachment to the organization, while continuance and normative commitments are considered more behavioral. In other words, the level of commitment an employee has toward an organization can vary. An employee's decision to remain with the organization during both favorable and

challenging times reflects the nature of their commitment (Mahdavi, Arabi, & Mahmoudi, 2014). In summary, employee commitment is defined as “an attachment to the organization, characterized by the intention to remain in it; an identification with the values and goals of the organization; and a willingness to exert extra effort on its behalf” (Porter et al., 1974, p. 604).

Affective Organizational Commitment

One of the management concerns is employees' commitment to the organization because it is only through their commitment that organizational objectives can be achieved (Ulabor & Bosede, 2019). Employees' commitment depends on various organizational factors such as leadership style, management style, nature of work, length of service, and other factors that may influence their decision to stay with the organization (Ulabor & Bosede, 2019). Consequently, the work environment becomes a significant concern for management that requires serious attention. A study by Deepak (2020) suggested that the psychosocial work environment influences affective organizational commitment. According to Mercurio (2015), the essence of organizational commitment is affective commitment. Emotional attachment to the organization is a critical aspect of organizational commitment because it has a significant correlation with retention and organizational performance (Mercurio, 2015). Meyer and Allen (1997) define affective commitment as an employee's perceived emotional attachment to their organization. An employee develops an emotional attachment to an organization when their values and priorities align with the company's values and mission (Lowry, 1973). Meyer et al. (2012) suggest that affective commitment occurs when an employee is emotionally attached to the organization and chooses to stay with it.

To achieve high-quality performance, organizations need highly motivated and committed employees, which requires detailed attention to various aspects of organizational operation, including economic and social exchanges in the employee-organization relationship (Alcover et al., 2020). The study by Alcover et al. (2020) found that team performance is influenced by team autonomous motivation and affective commitment. This finding aligns with earlier research by Jantan (2018), which found that pay, promotion, team support, and intrinsic motivation (such as autonomy and participation in decision-making) correlate with affective commitment. According to Lowry (1973), emotional attachment is a crucial element in sustaining employees' active involvement in helping the organization. Johnson and Chang (2006) found that employees with affective commitment tend to exert more effort for the benefit of the organization compared to those with lower affective commitment. Employees with high affective commitment generally exhibit higher intrinsic motivation and a strong personal desire to remain loyal to the organization. Thus, management can increase affective commitment by following Abraham Maslow's advice, as cited by Lowry (1973): "Give people affection and security, and they will give affection and be secure in their feelings and their behavior." This approach is one way to attract and retain skilled talent, which is essential for a company's competitiveness (Aguirre, Post, & Hewlett, 2009; Alvino, 2014). In the face of uncertainties and competition, focusing on employee commitment is crucial (Cohen, 2007; Gibb, 2011; Meyer et al., 2002). Alvino (2014) notes that working long hours and productivity are influenced by emotional attachment or commitment to an organization's mission. This is supported by Akinyemi's (2012) study, which found that organizational citizenship behavior is influenced by affective organizational commitment. Employees who have an emotional attachment to the organization are more likely to exert extra effort beyond their formal job descriptions to assist the organization and their colleagues.

Studies have examined the effect of affective commitment on employees' work performance. Hashmi, Ahmad, and Nawaz (2021) and Ullah, Kamran, Akram, Nawaz, and Rehman (2021) found that employees with high affective commitment exhibit greater work dedication, accept organizational objectives, and contribute to the organization's success. Similarly, Javeria (2013) and Khan and Iqbal (2020b) discovered that employees with high levels of affective commitment tend to be happier and more committed than those with lower affective commitment.

Continuance Commitment

Reasons for employees to stay will not always depend solely on affective commitment. Some employees are practical in their decision-making. They choose to act when it is beneficial for them or decide to stay if they find it economically advantageous. Their decisions reflect the type of commitment they have. According to Meyer et al. (2012), when an employee considers the cost before deciding to leave or stay, they are engaging in continuance commitment. An employee is willing to stay with the company as a result of a cost-benefit analysis, where they believe they will lose more by leaving than by staying (Allen & Meyer, 1990; Halis, 2021). The employee decides to stay after evaluating the pros and cons and chooses to be loyal because they believe it is more advantageous to remain than to leave (Cohen, 2007; Nawaz, Afzal, & Shehzadi, 2013). Leaving the company means losing their investment, friends, familiar environment, benefits, and facing the risk of unemployment (Allen & Meyer, 1990; Meyer & Allen, 1984).

Continuance commitment (CC) is also important for the organization because it influences employees' decisions to stay. Management must pay serious attention to strategies for retaining employees over the long term. While an employer may not always be able to develop programs that attract employees emotionally, they can create programs that encourage employees to stay for economic reasons. Pay and benefits are relevant issues in continuance commitment. Several studies have examined the effect of continuance commitment on organizational performance. Sukanebari and Konya (2020) and Ehijiele (2018) found a significant correlation between organizational commitment and performance, recommending that management should focus on employee pay and benefits. Kuhl et al. (2020), Parvee (2019), Metin and Asli (2018), and Effiong (2017) also demonstrated that continuance commitment, based on economic reasons, affects job performance. Although not all employees remain loyal to the organization solely because of benefits, the importance of continuance commitment to the organization deserves attention. Suliman and Iles (2000) argued that continuance commitment is crucial because it affects job performance and, consequently, organizational success. Their study also noted that continuance commitment is unrelated to sex, education, job status, and organizational tenure.

Normative Commitment

As pointed out, the reasons why employees stay loyal to an organization can vary from person to person. Their willingness to stay and fulfill their duties can be measured by their level of attachment and commitment to the organization. Their eagerness to achieve organizational objectives also indicates their commitment (Khan et al., 2021). Manifested behaviors express their commitments, whether affective, continuance, or normative (Khan et al., 2021). While affective commitment refers to emotional attachment to the organization and continuance commitment results from a cost-benefit analysis, normative commitment arises from a sense of moral obligation (Meyer & Allen, 1991). Employees stay with the company because they feel morally obliged to do so (Muhammad et al., 2021). They remain with the organization out of a moral obligation, even at the expense of job satisfaction (Messner, 2013; Iverson & Buttigieg, 1999; Singh & Gupta, 2015). Violating organizational norms is considered morally wrong, particularly when the company has policies that require employees to honor their employment contract (Marsh & Mannari, 1977). Wiener (1982, p. 421) describes commitment as reflecting "the totality of internalized normative pressures to act in a way that meets organizational goals and interests." Employees believe that adhering to organizational rules and norms is the right and moral course of action, even at a personal sacrifice. Meyer and Parfyonova (2010) define normative commitment as a "mindset obligation" to remain with the organization and support its initiatives based on moral obligation, distinct from affective commitment (AC), which is based on emotional attachment, and continuance commitment (CC), which is based on cost-benefit analysis. All these types of commitment are important for management to consider. According to Meyer and Allen (1991, p. 67), "Employees who have high normative commitment will be loyal to the organization because they believe that it is the right and moral thing to do."

Research on the importance of normative commitment for supporting performance and organizational success has produced mixed results. Some studies suggest that normative commitment does not always correlate with work performance and organizational performance (Metin & Asli, 2018; Jakada et al., 2019; Parveen, 2019; Oyeniyi, 2017; Genevičiūtė-Janonienė & Endriulaitienė, 2013). Conversely, Nguyen et al. (2020) found that normative commitment directly impacts employees' motivation and indirectly affects job performance through opportunistic behavior and knowledge sharing. This finding is supported by Stackhouse et al. (2022), Ahmad et al. (2014), Rebeka (2019), Anugrah and Priyambodo (2021), Dinc (2017), and Kuhal et al. (2020), who found that the three components of organizational commitment are significantly correlated with job satisfaction and organizational performance. The contradictory results may be due to varying organizational cultures or environments that influence organizational commitment (Suradi, 2019; Dias et al., 2021).

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: The conceptual framework reflects the influence of attitude toward work on organizational commitment. Affective and cognitive attitudes can affect affective, continuance and normative commitment.

Statement of the Problem

The study determined the influence of affective and cognitive attitudes toward work on organizational commitment along with affective, continuance and normative commitment. It specifically answered the following questions:

1. What are the attitudes employees toward their work in terms of:
 - a. Affective attitude
 - b. Cognitive attitude

2. What is the organizational commitment of employees:
 - a. Affective commitment
 - b. Continuance commitment
 - c. Normative commitment

3. Is there a relationship between attitude toward work and the organizational commitment of the employees?

Assumption

Human behaviour is influenced by his/her attitude toward a certain object of attitude and it can be measured (Thurstone, 1928). His/her behaviour is influenced by what he/she feels and what he/she knows about the attitude object. Positive and negative attitude affects how he/she treats the object attitude.

Hypothesis

Studies have been conducted determining the effect of attitude toward work on job performance and job satisfaction, and these studies concluded that attitude influences work performance and job satisfaction (Abdalkrim, 2016, Susanty, et al., 2013). In the same vein, the current study hypothesizes that attitude toward work affects organizational commitment.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

The study limits its investigation only to the two dimensions of attitude which are affective and cognitive attitude and measures their effects on the organizational commitment which are limited to affective, continuance and normative organizational commitment of the employees of the Divine Word College of Laoag.

Research Methodology

As a requirement for scientific inquiry, research must follow a certain methodology of investigation. The methodology reflects how the study went through identifying, selecting, processing, and analyzing information about a topic (Wilkinson, 2000, Leedy, 1974). This is a must-follow procedure to be called scientific and for the study to be valid. The study follows the rule of procedures in the investigation by determining the research design, data gathering instruments method, the population of the study, the locale of the study, the data gathering procedures, and statistical treatment of data.

Research Design of the Study

The study applied a descriptive assessment, and correlational research design to determine the attitude of employees toward work and organizational commitment. Ariola (2006) contended that a descriptive correlation study is intended to describe the relationship among variables without seeking to establish a causal connection. While descriptive research is simply to describe a population, a situation, or a phenomenon. It is also used to describe profiles, frequency distribution, describe characteristics of people, situations, or phenomena. In short, it answers the question of what, when, how, where, and not why question (McCombes, 2020).

The Locale of the Study

The locale of the study was Divine Word College of Laoag in Ilocos Norte.

Population

The respondents of the study are all employees of the Divine Word College of Laoag in the Ilocos Norte. Since the number of employees is limited, therefore, the total enumeration sampling was used and thus all employees and administrators were taken as respondents to the study.

Data Gathering instruments

The data were gathered through adopted research questionnaires. Questionnaires on attitude toward work are adapted from Abun, et al.(2021) and questionnaires on organizational commitment from Allen and Meyer (1990) as cited by Abdullah (2011).

Data Gathering Procedures

The integrity and quality of research do not depend only on the content but also on the process of how the study is carried out. It has to be done through the right process. Concerning this study, before the researcher distributed the questionnaires, a letter was sent to the President of the college to allow the researcher to float his questionnaires in

their respective institutions. In the process of collecting the data, the researcher requests employees' representatives to retrieve the data from different individual employees before they are submitted to the researcher.

Ethical Procedures

The study was carried out after the research ethics committee examined and approved the procedures and content of the paper if it did not violate ethical standards and if it did not cause harm to human life and the environment.

Statistical Treatment of Data

To analyze the data, the descriptive and inferential statistic was used. The weighted mean was used to determine the level of attitude toward work and organizational commitment and the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to measure the correlation between attitude toward work and organizational commitment.

The following ranges of values with their descriptive interpretation will be used:

<i>Statistical Range</i>	<i>Descriptive Interpretation</i>
4.21-5.00	strongly agree/Very High
3.41-4.20	Agree/High
2.61-3.40	somewhat agree/moderate
1.81-2.60	Disagree/Low
1.00-1.80	Strongly disagree/Very Low

Data Presentation and Analysis

The data presentation follows the statement of the problems of the study.

Problem 1: What is the cognitive and affective attitude of employees toward their work?

Table 1. The cognitive and affective attitude of the employees towards their work (n=161)

ATTITUDES TOWARD WORK		WEIGHTED MEAN	DESCRIPTIVE INTERPRETATION
A. Cognitive Attitude			
1.	I think I know my work.	4.04	A/H
2.	I think that I have the knowledge to perform my work.	3.90	A/H
3.	I think that I have enough experience to carry out my tasks.	3.86	A/H
4.	I think that I am familiar with all the details of my work.	3.88	A/H
5.	I think that I have the skills to carry out my work.	3.92	A/H
6.	I think I can carry out my work without the help of others	3.74	A/H
Composite Mean		3.89	A/H
B. Affective Attitude			
1.	I feel happy with my work.	3.85	A/H
2.	I love the work I am doing.	3.79	A/H
3.	My work gives me satisfaction.	3.83	A/H
4.	I feel good because my work matches my skills.	3.88	A/H
5.	My work is important to me.	3.94	A/H
6.	My work gives me a sense of meaning	3.98	A/H
Composite Mean		3.88	A/H
OVERALL MEAN		3.88	A/H

Source: Rosenberg and Hovland (1960).

Legend:

Range of Mean Values

Descriptive Interpretation

4.21 - 5.00	Strongly agree/Very high
3.41 - 4.20	Agree/high
2.61 - 3.40	Somewhat agree/Moderate
1.81 - 2.60	Disagree /low
1.00 - 1.80	Strongly disagree/ very low

Based on the data in the table, the overall cognitive and affective attitudes of employees toward work received a mean rating of 3.88, which is categorized as "agree" or "high." This rating suggests that both cognitive and affective attitudes toward work are neither very high nor very low, but rather fall into the high range. When considered separately, the cognitive attitude and affective attitude were rated similarly, at 3.89 and 3.88, respectively. In terms of cognitive attitude, employees agree that they possess the skills and knowledge necessary for their work. Regarding affective attitude, employees also agree that they are happy and find meaning in their work, which contributes to their overall satisfaction.

Abun et al. (2021) highlighted the positive impact of cognitive and affective attitudes toward work on job performance. Shipria et al. (2021) specifically argued that positive emotions toward work enhance employee performance, while Addous et al. (2018) emphasized the crucial role of knowledge in boosting both individual and organizational performance. Therefore, improving employees' attitudes toward work is a key responsibility for management.

Problem 2. What is the organizational commitment of employees:

- a. *Affective commitment*
- b. *Continuance commitment*
- c. *Normative commitment*

Table 2. Organizational commitment of employees (n=161)

	ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT	WEIGHTED MEAN	DESCRIPTIVE INTERPRETATION
A.	Affective Commitment		
1.	I would be very happy to spend the rest of my career in this organization	3.88	A/H
2.	I feel as if this organization's problems are my own	3.74	A/H
3.	I feel like 'part of my family at this organization	3.70	A/H
4.	I feel 'emotionally attached to this organization	3.73	A/H
5.	This organization has a great deal of personal meaning for me.	3.88	A/H
6.	I feel a strong sense of belonging to this organization	3.68	A/H
	Composite Mean	3.77	A/H
B.	Continuance Commitment		
1.	It would be very hard for me to leave my job at this organization right now even if I wanted to	3.72	A/H
2.	Too much of my life would be disrupted if I left my organization	3.46	A/H
3.	Right now, staying with my job at this organization is a matter of necessity as much as desire	3.63	A/H
4.	I believe I have too few options to consider leaving this organization	3.63	A/H

5.	One of the few negative consequences of leaving my job at this organization would be the scarcity of available alternatives elsewhere.	3.57	A/H
6.	One of the major reasons I continue to work for this organization is that leaving would require considerable personal sacrifice	3.70	A/H
	Composite Mean	3.62	A/H
C. Normative Commitment			
1.	I should remain with my organization.	3.62	A/H
2.	Even if it were to my advantage, I do not feel it would be right to leave.	3.49	A/H
3.	I would feel guilty if I left this organization now	3.62	A/H
4.	This organization deserves my loyalty	3.73	A/H
5.	I would not leave my organization right now because of my sense of obligation to it	3.75	A/H
6.	I owe a great deal to this organization	3.85	A/H
	Composite Mean	3.68	A/H
OVERALL MEAN		3.69	A/H

Source: Meyer and Allen (1997)

Organizational commitment is a crucial factor in managing organizational performance. The data shows that overall organizational commitment among employees received a mean rating of 3.69, categorized as "agree" or "high." This rating indicates that employees' organizational commitment is high but not exceptionally high or low. When examined individually, the dimensions of organizational commitment were rated consistently, with mean scores of 3.77, 3.66, and 3.68, respectively, all reflecting high levels. Employees report a strong emotional attachment to the institution, feeling that it has become an integral part of their lives. Consequently, they prefer to continue their service, recognizing that leaving would cause significant disruption in their lives.

Stackhouse et al. (2022) highlighted that employee commitment is essential for enhancing organizational performance and achieving goals. Similarly, Nasir and Islam (2017) and Mesa et al. (2019) emphasized that improving employees' organizational commitment is a critical responsibility for management.

Problem 3. Is there a relationship between attitude toward work and the organizational commitment of the employees?

a. Attitude Toward Work and Affective Commitment

The multiple linear regression analysis done indicated that affective attitude and cognitive attitude toward work taken together significantly predicted the employees' affective commitment to the organization, $F(2,157) = 16.507$, $p < .05$, with 17.40 per cent overlap between the predictor variables (affective attitude and cognitive attitude toward work) and the outcome variable (affective commitment). When predicting the affective commitment of the employees, the error is approximately 0.66 rating points.

Specifically, cognitive attitude $B = .383$, $p < .05$, 2.206 quantified the Y-intercept for the regression equation.

Therefore, both affective attitude and cognitive attitude toward the work of the employees together could predict the employees' affective commitment to the organization.

However, when affective attitude and cognitive attitude toward work were considered singly, it was only cognitive attitude towards work which could predict the employees' affective commitment to the organization.

Hence, the observed differences in the employees' affective commitment to the organization are attributed to their cognitive attitude towards work.

Table 3: Attitude Toward Work and Affective Commitment

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.417 ^a	.174	.163	.66834

a. Predictors: (Constant), Affective Attitude, Cognitive Attitude

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	14.747	2	7.373	16.507	.000 ^b
	Residual	70.128	157	.447		
	Total	84.875	159			

a. Dependent Variable: Affective Commitment

b. Predictors: (Constant), Affective Attitude, Cognitive Attitude

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.206	.287		7.684	.000
	Cognitive Attitude	.383	.105	.401	3.654	.000
	Affective Attitude	.019	.100	.020	.187	.852

a. Dependent Variable: Affective Commitment

b. Attitude Toward Work and Continuance Commitment

Based on the multiple linear regression analysis, it was found that cognitive and affective attitudes toward the work of the employees significantly predicted their continuance commitment to the organization, $F(2,157) = 15.349$, $p < .05$ with 16.40 per cent overlap between the predictor variables and the outcome variable. When predicting the continuance commitment of the employees, the error is approximately 0.75 rating points.

Specifically, affective attitude $B = .312$, $p < .05$, 1.900 quantified the Y-intercept for the regression equation.

Therefore, when both cognitive and affective attitudes toward the work of the employees were considered together, they could predict the continuance commitment of the employees to the organization.

Hence, the differences observed in the employees' continuance commitment to the organization are attributed to the differences in their cognitive and affective attitudes toward work.

However, when cognitive and affective attitudes toward the work of the employees were treated separately, it was only affective attitudes towards work which could predict their continuance commitment to the organization.

Table 5: Attitude Toward Work and Continuance Commitment

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.404 ^a	.164	.153	.75512

a. Predictors: (Constant), Affective Attitude, Cognitive Attitude

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	17.505	2	8.752	15.349	.000 ^b
	Residual	89.524	157	.570		
	Total	107.028	159			

a. Dependent Variable: Continuance Commitment

b. Predictors: (Constant), Affective Attitude, Cognitive Attitude

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.900	.324		5.856	.000
	Cognitive Attitude	.131	.118	.122	1.106	.270
	Affective Attitude	.312	.113	.305	2.756	.007

a. Dependent Variable: Continuance Commitment

c. Attitude Toward Work and Normative Commitment

The employees' cognitive and affective attitudes toward work when taken together could not significantly predict their normative commitment to the organization, $F(2,157) = 0.138, p > .05$ with 0.02 per cent overlap between the predictor and outcome variables.

Therefore, the observed differences in the employees' normative commitment to the organization are not due to their cognitive and affective attitudes toward work. Thus, their normative commitment to the organization remains the same regardless of the variations in their cognitive and affective attitudes toward work.

Table 6: Attitude toward work and normative commitment

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.042 ^a	.002	-.011	.69735

a. Predictors: (Constant), Affective Attitude, Cognitive Attitude

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.135	2	.067	.138	.871 ^b
	Residual	76.348	157	.486		
	Total	76.483	159			

a. Dependent Variable: Normative Commitment

b. Predictors: (Constant), Affective Attitude, Cognitive Attitude

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		

	(Constant)	3.523	.300		11.762	.000
1	Cognitive Attitude	.030	.109	.033	.271	.787
	Affective Attitude	.010	.105	.011	.095	.925

a. Dependent Variable: Normative Commitment

Discussion

The study results reveal that both affective and cognitive attitudes toward work, as well as organizational commitment among employees, are rated as high. Correlation analysis shows a significant relationship between cognitive and affective attitudes toward work and both affective and continuance organizational commitment, though no significant correlation is found with normative commitment. This finding suggests that management should focus on strategies to boost organizational commitment by enhancing employees' affective and cognitive attitudes toward their work. School administrators should explore methods to develop these attitudes, as improving employees' mental perspectives and feelings about their work is crucial for fostering stronger organizational commitment. Positive attitudes and feelings are key motivational factors that influence employees' behavior and performance in their roles. This is supported by Svenningsson et al. (2022), Abun et al. (2019), and Vamvaka et al. (2020), who emphasize the significant impact of affective and cognitive attitudes on work performance.

Conclusion

Based on the problem statement and study objectives, it can be concluded that employees' affective and cognitive attitudes toward their work, as well as their overall organizational commitment, are rated as high. There is a significant correlation between these attitudes and organizational commitment overall. However, when examined individually, no correlation is found between these attitudes and normative organizational commitment. This indicates that variations in normative organizational commitment are not influenced by employees' affective and cognitive attitudes toward their work.

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Authors' Contribution: Conceptualization: D.A., F.P.J. **Methodology:** D.A., F.P.J., ... **Data collection:** D.A., F.P.J., ... **Formal Analysis:** D.A., F.P.J., ... **Writing-Review and Editing:** D.A., F.P.J., ...

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References

Abdalkarim, G.M. (2016). Attitude toward Work, Job satisfaction, and job performance. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 6(12). <https://doi.org/10.6007/IJARBS/v6-i12/2547>

- Abun, D., Ubasa, A.L.A., Magallanes, T., Encarnacion, M.J. & Ranay, F.B. (2021). Attitude toward the work and its influence on individual work performance of employees: basis for attitude management. *Technium Social Science Journal*, 18(1).
- Abun, D., Magallanes, T. & Encarnacion, M.J. (2019). College students' cognitive and affective attitude toward higher education and their academic engagement. *International Journal of English, Literature and Social Science (IJELS)*, 4(5), <https://doi.org/10.22161/ijels.45.38>
- Abun, D., Magallanes, T., Marlene, T.N. Julian, F.P. & Madamba, M.B. (2021). Effect of attitude toward work, and work environment on the employees' self-efficacy. *International Journal of Research in Business & Social Science*, 10(7), 129-141.
- Addous, H.A., Al Sokkar, A. & Blaquees, I. (2018). The impact of knowledge management on the performance. *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science*, 9(4). <https://doi.org/10.14569/IJACSA.2018.090432>
- Aguirre, D., Post, L., & Hewlett, S. A. (2009). The talent innovation imperative. *Strategy+ business*, 56, 39-49.
- Ahmad, N., Iqbal, N., Javed, K. & Hamad, N. (2014). Impact of organizational commitment and employee performance on employee satisfaction. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 1(1), 84-92.
- Ajzen, I., & Fishbein, M. (1970). The prediction of behaviour from attitudinal and normative variables. *Journal of Experimental Social Psychology*, 6, 466–487. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-1031\(70\)90057-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-1031(70)90057-0)
- Ajzen, I. & Fishbein, M. (1975). *Belief, attitude, intention, and behaviour: an introduction to theory and research*. Addison-Wesley Publishing Company
- Ajzen, I. & Fishbein, M. (1980). *Understanding attitude and predicting social behaviour*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall.
- Ajzen, I. (1988). *Attitudes, personality, and behaviour*. Open University Press.
- Ajzen, I., & Driver, B. L. (1991). Prediction of leisure participation from behavioural, normative, and control beliefs: An application of the theory of planned behaviour. *Leisure Sciences*, 13, 185-204. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01490409109513137>
- Ajzen, I. (1991). The theory of planned behaviour. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 50(2). [https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978\(91\)90020-T](https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978(91)90020-T)
- Ajzen, I., & Driver, B. L. (1992). Application of the theory of planned behaviour to leisure choice. *Journal of Leisure Research*, 24, 207–224. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00222216.1992.11969889>
- Ajzen, I., & Driver, B. L. (1992). Application of the theory of planned behaviour to leisure choice. *Journal of Leisure Research*, 24, 207-224.179-211. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978\(91\)90020-T](https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978(91)90020-T)
- Ajzen, I., & Sexton, J. (1999). *Depth of processing, belief congruence, and attitude-behaviour correspondence*. In S. Chaiken & Y. Trope (Eds.). *Dual-process theories in social psychology* (pp. 117–138). Guilford
- Ajzen, I., & Fishbein, M. (2000). *Attitudes and the attitude-behaviour relation: reasoned and automatic processes*. In W. Stroebe & M. Hewstone (Eds.). *European Review of Social Psychology* (Vol. 11, pp. 1–33). Wiley

- Ajzen, I. (2002). Perceived Behavioral Control, Self-Efficacy, Locus of Control, and the Theory of Planned Behavior. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 32(4). <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1559-1816.2002.tb00236.x>
- Ajzen, I. & Fishbein, M. (2005). *The influence of attitude on behaviour*. In book: *the handbook of attitudes*. Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Ajzen, I., & Fishbein, M. (1977). Attitude-behaviour relations: a theoretical analysis and review of empirical research. *Psychological Bulletin*, 84, 888–918. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.84.5.888>
- Ajzen, I. (1993). *New directions in attitude measurement*. Walter de Gruyter.
- Akinyemi, B. (2012). The influence of affective commitment on citizenship behaviour and intention to quit among commercial banks' employees in Nigeria. *Journal of Management and Sustainability*, 2(2). <https://doi.org/10.5539/jms.v2n2p54>
- Albarracín, D., & Wyer, R. S., Jr (2000). The cognitive impact of past behaviour: influences on beliefs, attitudes, and future behavioural decisions. *Journal of personality and social psychology*, 79(1), 5–22. <https://doi.org/10.1037//0022-3514.79.1.5>
- Alcover, C.M., Chambel, M.J. & Estreder, Y. (2020). Monetary incentives, motivational orientation and affective commitment in contact centres: A multilevel mediation model. *Journal of Economic Psychology*, 8, 102307. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joep.2020.102307>.
- Allameh, S.M., Shahriari, M., Mansoori, H. (2012). Investigating employee attitude toward organization, organizational climate and employee engagement as antecedents of organizational citizenship behaviour. *Australian Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*, 6(8), 384-393.
- Allen, N.J. & Meyer, J.P. (1990). The measurement and antecedence of affective, continuance and normative commitment to the organization. *Journal of Occupational Psychology*, 63, 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2044-8325.1990.tb00506.x>
- Altmann, T. (2008). Attitude: concept and analysis. *Nursing Forum*, 43(3). <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1744-6198.2008.00106.x>
- Alvino, L. (2014, 29 September). Engage your employees or lose billions. *Forbes Magazine*. Retrieved from <http://www.forbes.com/sites/womensmedia/2014/09/29/engage-your-employees-or-lose-billions/>
- Anugrah, P.G. & Priyambodo, A.B. (2021). Correlation between organizational commitment and employee performance when working from home during the COVID-19 pandemic. *KnE Social Sciences: International Conference of Psychology, 2021*.
- APA Dictionary of Psychology (n.d). *Attitude*. Retrieved April 15, 2024, from <https://dictionary.apa.org/attitude>
- Appiah, K. A. (2021). *The Philosophy of Work*. In David Sobel, Peter Vallentyne, and Steven Wall (eds). *Oxford studies in political philosophy*. volume 7. Online edn, Oxford Academic Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780192897480.003.0001>
- Ariola, M.M. (2006). *Principles and methods of research*. National Bookstore
- Bandura, A. (1991). *Self-regulation of motivation through anticipatory and self-regulatory mechanisms*. In R. A. Dienstbier (ed.). *Perspectives on Motivation: Nebraska Symposium on Motivation* (Vol. 38, pp. 69 – 164). The University of Nebraska Press

Brügger A and Höchli B (2019). The role of attitude strength in behavioural spillover: attitude matters—but not necessarily as a moderator. *Frontier in Psychology*, 10, 1018. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.01018>.

Cambridge Dictionary (n.d). *Attitude*. Retrieved April 20, 2024 from <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/us/dictionary/english/attitude>

Campbell, A., Converse, P. E., Miller, W. E., & Stokes, D. E. (1960). *The American voter*. Wiley.

Chaiklin, H. (2011). Attitudes, behaviour, and social practice. *The Journal of Sociology & Social Welfare*, 38(1).

Cherry, K. (2022). Attitude in psychology: definition, formation, changes. *Very Well Mind*. Retrieved May 15, 2024, from <https://www.verywellmind.com/attitudes-how-they-form-change-shape-behavior-2795897>

Cholbi, M. (2022). Philosophical approach to work and labor. *Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy*. Retrieved from <https://plato.stanford.edu>

Cohen A. (2007). Commitment before and after: an evaluation and reconceptualization of organizational commitment. *Human Resource Management Review*, 17, 336-354. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hrmr.2007.05.001>

Deepak, S. (2020). Psycho-social work environment influences on the affective organizational commitment-an empirical investigation in the information technology industry. *International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research*, 9(3).

Dias, A.L., Silva, V., Pereira, L.F. & Goncalves, R.A.H. (2021). Organizational environment and organizational commitment. *International Journal of Services and Operations Management*, 2(3). <https://doi.org/10.3390/socsci11090406>

Dinc, M.S. (2017). Organizational commitment components and job performance: the mediating role of job satisfaction. *Pakistan Journal of Commerce and Social Sciences*, 11 (3), 773-789.

Dollard, J. (1949). Under what conditions do opinions predict behaviour? *Public Opinion Quarterly*, 12(4), 623-632.

Eagly, A.H. & Chaiken, S. (1993). *The Psychology of Attitudes*. Harcourt Brace Jovanovich

Eagly, A. H., & Chaiken, S. (2005). *Attitude research in the 21st century: the current state of knowledge*. In D. Albarracín, B. T. Johnson, & M. P. Zanna (Eds.). *The Handbook of Attitudes* (pp. 743–767). Lawrence Erlbaum Associates Publishers.

Effiong, M. (2017). *Organizational commitment and employee performance. Factors that promote positive motivational behaviour among the employees*. Grin Verlag.

Ehijiele, E. (2018). The influence of employees' commitment on organizational performance in Nigeria. *International Journal of Research Publication*, 2(1), 1-12.

Ferguson, M. J., Bargh, J. A., & Nayak, D. A. (2005). After-affects: how automatic evaluations influence the interpretation of subsequent, unrelated stimuli. *Journal of Experimental Social Psychology*, 41(2), 182–191. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jesp.2004.05.008>

Festinger, L. (1957). *A theory of cognitive dissonance*. Stanford University Press.

French, D.P., Sutton, S., Hennings, S.J., Mitchell, J., Wareham, N.J., Griffin, S., Hardeman, W., &

Kinmonth, L. (2005). The importance of affective beliefs and attitudes in the theory of planned behaviour: predicting intention to increase physical activity. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 35(9), 1824–1848. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1559-1816.2005.tb02197.x> 35(9).

Frymier, B. & Nadler, M.K. (2017). *The relationship between attitudes and behaviours*. Property of Kendall Hunt Publishing.

Genevičiūtė-Janonienė, G. & Endriulaitienė, A. (2013). Employees' organizational commitment: its negative aspects for organizations. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* 140, 558 – 564. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.04.470>

Gibb S. (2011). *Human resource development*. Palgrave Macmillan

Gilbert, Evelyn Sukanebari & Dr. K. T. Konya. (2020). Continuance commitment and organizational performance of manufacturing firms in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Social Sciences & Humanities Research* 8(1):80-91

Godin, G. (1987). Importance of the emotional aspect of attitude to predict intention. *Psychological Reports*, 61, 719-723. <https://doi.org/10.2466/pr0.1987.61.3.719>

Gouldner, A. W. (1960). The norm of reciprocity: a preliminary statement. *American Sociological Review*, 161-178. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2092623>

Greenwald, A., Brook, T.C. & Ostrom, T.M. (1966). *On Defining attitude and attitude theory*. Elsevier.

Halis, M. (2021). *The relationship between organizational culture and organizational commitment: research in private health institutions*. In *Handbook of research on representing health and medicine in modern media*. IGI Global Publisher of Timely Knowledge.

Hashmi, A., Ahmad, M. A., & Nawaz, M. A. (2021). The role of coordination, decision making and special data infrastructure on the disaster management in Pakistan: moderating role of information system. *Review of Applied Management and Social Sciences*, 4(1), 79-91.

Heberlein, T. A., & Black, J. S. (1976). Attitudinal specificity and the prediction of behaviour in a field setting. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 33(4), 474–479. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.33.4.474>

Hogg, M., & Vaughan, G. (2005). *Social psychology* (4th ed.). Prentice-Hall.

Iverson, R. D., & Buttigieg, D. M. (1999). Affective, normative and continuance commitment: Can the “right kind” of commitment be managed? *Journal of Management Studies*, 36(3), 307-333. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-6486.00138>

Jakada, M.B., Jakada, A.H., Hussein, M.A., Kurawa, N.S. & Rabi, A. (2019). Effect of affective, continuance, and normative commitment on job performance of employees of National Identity Management Commission, Northwest Zone, Nigeria. *Lapai International Journal of Management and Social Sciences*, 11(2).

James H. Myers, J.H. & Alpert, M.I. (1977). *Semantic confusion in attitude research: salience Vs. importance Vs. determinants*. In *NA - Advances in consumer research, Volume 04*, eds. William D. Perreault, Jr. Atlanta, GA: Association for Consumer Research, 106-110.

- Jantan, M. S. (2018). *Correlation between rewards and commitment: an empirical investigation of independent financial adviser in Malaysia*. Thesis. Retrieved April 29, 2024, from <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3560753> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3560753>
- Javeria, A. (2013). Examining the antecedents of job satisfaction and further its impact on organizational commitment. *Journal of Public Administration and Governance*, 3(3), 317-334. <https://doi.org/10.5296/jpag.v3i3.6224>
- Johnson, R.E. & Chang, C.H. (2006). "I" is to Continuance as "we" are too Affective: the relevance of the self-concepts for organizational commitment. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 27, 549-570. <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.364>
- Kaiser, F. G., & Wilson, M. (2019). The Campbell paradigm is a behavior-predictive reinterpretation of the classical tripartite model of attitudes. *European Psychologist*, 24(4), 359–374. <https://doi.org/10.1027/1016-9040/a000364>
- Kan, M.P.H., & Fabrigar, L.R. (2017). *Theory of planned behaviour*. In: Zeigler-Hill, V., Shackelford, T. (eds). Encyclopedia of personality and individual differences. Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-28099-8_1191-1
- Khan, A. J., & Iqbal, J. (2020a). Do high-performance work practices increase the organizational performance of public sector Companies? An Investigation of Mediation Mechanism. *Pakistan Journal of Social Sciences (PJSS)*, 40(2), 1007-1021.
- Khan, A. J., & Iqbal, J. (2020b). Training and employee commitment: the social exchange perspective. *Journal of Management Sciences*, 7(1), 88-100. <https://doi.org/10.20547/jms.2014.2007106>
- Khan, A.J., Bashir, F., Nasim, I. & Ahmad, R. (2021). Understanding affective, normative & continuance commitment through the lens of training & development. *iRASD Journal of Management*, 3(2), 105-113.
- Kraus, S. J. (1995). Attitudes and the prediction of behaviour: a meta-analysis of the empirical literature. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, 21(1), 58–75. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0146167295211007>
- Krech, D., & Crutchfield, R. S. (1948). *Theory and problems of social psychology*. McGraw-Hill Book Company, Inc.
- Kuhal, A.J., Arabi, A., Zaid, M.F.M. & Ismawi, N. (2020). Relationship between affective commitment, continuance commitment and normative commitment towards job performance. *Journal of Sustainable Management Studies*, 1(1), 19-27.
- Kutner, B., Wilkins, C., & Yarrow, P. R. (1970). *Verbal attitudes and overt behaviour involving racial prejudice*. In G. F. Summers (Ed.). *Attitude measurement* (pp. 433-437). Rand McNally & Co
- LaPiere, R.T. (1934). Attitudes vs. actions. *Social Forces*, 13(2), 230-237. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2570339>
- Leedy, P.D. (1974). *Practical research: planning and design*. Macmillan
- Lewin, J. L. N. (1999). *Dance therapy notebook*. The Marian Chace Foundation.
- Lowe, R., Eves, F., & Carroll, D. (2002). The influence of affective and instrumental beliefs on exercise intentions and behaviour: a longitudinal analysis. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 32, 1241-1252. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1559-1816.2002.tb01434.x>

- Lowry R. J. (1973). *AH Maslow: An intellectual portrait*. Brooks/Cole
- Luthans, F. (2008). *Organizational behaviour*. McGraw-Hill, Irwin
- Mahdavi, M., Arab, M., & Mahmoudi, M. (2014). Organizational commitment and intention to leave among hospitals' employees in Tehran hospitals. *Journal of Hospital*, 12(4), 19-29.
- Maio, G. R., & Haddock, G. (2010). *How do attitudes influence behaviour?* SAGE Publications Ltd, <https://dx.doi.org/10.4135/9781446214299>
- Malhotra, N.K., (2005). Attitude and affect: new frontiers of research in the 21st century. *Journal of Business Research*, 58(4), 477–482. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0148-2963\(03\)00146-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0148-2963(03)00146-2)
- Marsh, R. M., & Mannari, H. (1977). Organizational commitment and turnover: a prediction study. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 22, 57–75. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2391746>
- McCombes, S. (2020). Descriptive Research. *Scibbr*. Retrieved April 4, 2024 from <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/descriptive-research/>
- McLeod, S. A. (2018). May 21). *Attitudes and behaviour*. *Simply Psychology*. Retrieved May 3, 2024, from www.simplypsychology.org/attitudes.html
- Mercurio, Z. A. (2015). Affective commitment as an essence of organizational commitment: an integrative literature review. *Human Resource Development Review*, 14(4), 389–414. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1534484315603612>
- Merriam-Webster. (n.d.). *Attitude*. In the *Merriam-Webster.com dictionary*. Retrieved January 4, 2023, from <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/attitude>
- Mesa, A.F., Llopis, O., Granero, A.G. & Penuela, J.O. (2019). *Enhancing organizational commitment through task significance: the moderating role of openness to experience*. Elsevier.
- Messner, W. (2013). Effect of Organizational Culture on employee commitment in the Indian IT services sourcing industry. *Journal of Indian Business Research*, 5(2), 76-100. <https://doi.org/10.1108/17554191311320764>
- Metin, K. & Asli, K. (2018). The relationship between organizational commitment and work performance: a case of industrial enterprises. *Journal of Economic and Social Development (JESD)*, 5(1).
- Meyer, J. P., & Allen, N. J. (1984). Testing the 'side-bet theory' of organizational commitment: some methodological considerations. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 69, 372–378. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.69.3.372>
- Meyer, J. P., & Allen, N. J. (1991). A three-component conceptualization of organizational commitment. *Human Resource Management Review*, 1(1), 61-89. [https://doi.org/10.1016/1053-4822\(91\)90011-Z](https://doi.org/10.1016/1053-4822(91)90011-Z)
- Meyer, J.P. & Allen, N.J. (1997). *Commitment in the workplace. Theory, research and application*. Sage
- Meyer J. P., Stanley D. J., Herscovitch L., Topolnytsky L. (2002). Affective, continuance, and normative commitment to the organization: a meta-analysis of antecedents, correlates, and consequences. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 61, 20-52. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jvbe.2001.1842>
- Meyer, J.P. & Parfyonova, N.M. (2010). Normative commitment in the workplace: a theoretical analysis and re-conceptualization. *Human Resource Management Review*, 20, 283-294. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hrmr.2009.09.001>

Meyer, J. P., Stanley, D. J., Jackson, T. A., McInnis, K. J., Maltin, E. R., & Sheppard, L. (2012). Affective, normative, and continuance commitment levels across cultures: A meta-analysis. *Journal of Vocational Behaviour*, 80(2), 225-245. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2011.09.005>

Millar, M.G. & Tesser, A. (1990). *Attitudes and behaviour: the cognitive-affective mismatch hypothesis*. *Advances in Consumer Research*, 17, 86-90.

Muhammad, S., Afridi, F. K., Ali, M. W., Shah, W. U., & Alasan, I. I. (2021). Effect of training on employee commitment: the mediating role of job satisfaction. *Pakistan Journal of Society, Education and Language (PJSEL)*, 7(1), 28-37

Muirhead, R. (2007). *Just work*. Harvard University Press.

Nazir, O. and Islam, J.U. (2017). Enhancing organizational commitment and employee performance through employee engagement: An empirical check. *South Asian Journal of Business Studies*, 6 (1), 98-114. <https://doi.org/10.1108/SAJBS-04-2016-0036>

Nawaz, M. A., Afzal, N., & Shehzadi, K. (2013). Problems of formally employed women: a case study of Bahawalnagar, Pakistan. *Asian Journal of Empirical Research*, 3(10), 1291-1299.

Nguyen, H.N., Tran, Q.B., & Nguyen, T.H. Y. (2020). The impact of organizational commitment on employee motivation: a study in Vietnamese enterprises. *The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 7(6), 439-447. <https://doi.org/10.13106/jafeb.2020.vol7.no6.439>

Olufemi, T.D. (2012). *Theories of attitude*. In C.D. Logans & M.I. Hodges (2012, Editors). *Hauppauge*. Nova Science Publishers, Inc.

O'Reilly, C. A., & Chatman, J. (1986). Organizational commitment and psychological attachment: The effects of compliance, identification, and internalization on prosocial behaviour. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 71(3), 492–499. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.71.3.492>

Oyeniya, K. O., Adeyemi, M. A., & Olaoye, B.O. (2017). Organizational commitment and employee's job performance: evidence from the Nigerian hospitality industry. *International Journal of Innovative Psychology & Social Development* 5(3), 15-22.

Oxford Languages (n.d). *Work*. Retrieved May 15, 2024 from <https://languages.oup.com/google-dictionary-en/>

Parveen, S. (2019). Exploring the impact of organizational commitment on employee performance. *International Journal of Business and Management Invention (IJBMI)*, 8(12), 25-34.

Pence, G. (2016). *Towards a Theory of Work*. In Schaff (ed.). *Philosophy and the problems of work*. EBSCO Publishing, 93–106.

Porter, L. W., Steers, R. M., Mowday, R. T., & Boulian, P. V. (1974). Organizational commitment, job satisfaction, and turnover among psychiatric technicians. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 59(5), 603-609. <https://doi.org/10.1037/h0037335>

Rebeka, K.P.E. (2019). Employee commitment on organizational performance. *International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering (IJRTE)*, 8(3).

Richard, A. (1998). *Work, philosophy of*. In *Encyclopedia of Philosophy*. Taylor & Francis. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780415249126-S068-1>.

- Rosenberg, M. J. (1956). Cognitive structure and attitudinal affect. *The Journal of Abnormal and Social Psychology*, 53(3), 367–372. <https://doi.org/10.1037/h0044579>
- Seel, N.M. (2012). *Attitudes – Formation and Change*. In: Seel, N.M. (eds). *Encyclopedia of the Sciences of Learning*. Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4419-1428-6_359
- Shripria, V., Srividya, V. & Kanishga, I. (2021). Emotions and their effect on the performance of employees in the job position as software developers, support engineers, testing and maintenance officers. *Turkish Online Journal of Qualitative Inquiry (TOJQI)*, 12(3), 300- 321.
- Singh, A., & Gupta, B. (2015). Job involvement, organizational commitment, professional commitment, and team commitment. *Benchmarking: An International Journal*, 22(6), 1192-1211. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BIJ-01-2014-0007>
- Smith, N.H. (2016). *Introduction: Philosophy of Work*. De Boeck Supérieur.
- Stackhouse, L. E., Zaman, F. M., & Turner, K. W. (2022). Effect of employee commitment on organizational performance; case of textile firms in Sweden. *Journal of Human Resource & Leadership*, 6(2), 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.53819/81018102t5074>
- Sukanebari, E. S., & Konya, K. T. (2020). Continuance commitment and organizational performance of manufacturing firms in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Social Sciences & Humanities Research*, 8(1), 80-91.
- Suliman, A. & Iles, P. (2000). The multidimensional nature of organizational commitment in a non-western context. *Journal of Management Development*, 19(1), 71-83. <https://doi.org/10.1108/02621710010308162>
- Suradi, S. (2019). The Effect of organizational culture on organizational commitment for participants in leadership education and training Level IV of the Ministry of finance. *International Journal of Multicultural and Multireligious Understanding*, 6(5).
- Susanty, A., Miradipta, R., & Jie, F. (2013). Analysis of the effect of attitude toward work, organizational commitment and job satisfaction on employee's job performance. *Jurnal Teknik Industri*, 15(1), 13-24.
- Svendsen, L.F. (2015). *Work*, 2nd edition. Routledge
- Svenningsson, J., Höst, G., Hultén, M. Hallstrom, J. (2022). Students' attitudes toward technology: exploring the relationship among affective, cognitive and behavioural components of the attitude construct. *International Journal of Technology and Design Education*, 32, 1531–1551 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10798-021-09657-7>
- Thurstone, L.L. (1928). Attitude can be measured. *American Journal of Sociology*, 33, 529-554. <https://doi.org/10.1086/214483>
- Thurstone, L.L., (1931). The measurement of attitudes. *Journal of Abnormal and Social Psychology*, 26, 249–269. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/h0070363>
- Tian, Z., Tang, C., Akram, F., Khan, M. L., & Chaudhry, M. A. (2022). Negative Work Attitudes and Task Performance: Mediating Role of Knowledge Hiding and Moderating Role of Servant Leadership. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 963696. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.963696>

Trafimow, D., Sheeran, P., Lombardo, B., Finlay, K. A., Brown, J., & Armitage, C. J. (2004). Affective and cognitive control of persons and behaviours. *British Journal of Social Psychology*, 43, 207-224. <https://doi.org/10.1348/0144666041501642>

Ulabor, E.A. & Bosed, A.I. (2019). Employee commitment and organizational performance in selected fast-food outlets in Osun State. *International Journal of Financial, Accounting, and Management (IJFAM)*, 1(1), 23-37.

Ullah, M., Kamran, H., Akram, S., Nawaz, M., & Rehman, F. (2021). Organizational antecedents and talent turnover: a relational analysis of credit card departments of banks. *Management Science Letters*, 11(4), 1211-1220

Unal, S. & Sari, I. (2012). Changing Students' Attitude toward L2 by Teaching Values in L2. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 70, 1413-1423.

Valois, P., Desharnais, R., & Godin, G. (1988). A comparison of the Fishbein and Ajzen and the Triandis attitudinal models for the prediction of exercise intention and behaviour. *Journal of Behavioral Medicine*, 11, 459-472. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00844839>

Wechsler, B. (1996). Organizational commitment: antecedents and outcomes in public organizations. *Public Productivity and Management Review*, 29, 256-277.

Wicker, A. (1969). Attitude versus action: the relationship of verbal and overt behavioural responses to attitude objects. *Journal of Social Issues*, 25(4), 41-78. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-4560.1969.tb00619.x>

Wiener, Y. (1982). Commitment in organizations: a normative view. *Academy of Management Review*, 7, 418-428. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2307/257334>

Wilkinson, D. (2000). *The researcher's toolkit: the complete guide to practitioner research*. Routledge

Zhou J, Dovidio J, Wang E (2013) How affectively-based and cognitively-based Attitudes drive intergroup behaviours: the moderating role of affective-cognitive consistency. *PLoS ONE* 8(11). e82150. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0082150>

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